

ISic3522

I.Sicily inscription 3522

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

aedicula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis of San Placido, sep.34

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3966

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Κορνήλιος
2. Μάγνος · Ἀ
3. παμεύς · ἰδί
4. ω · θρεπτῶ
5. Ἐπαφρύδι
6. μ(νήμης) · χ(άρις)

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001

Translation (en)

Cornelius Magnus of Apamea set this up for his adopted foundling, Epaphrus, for the sake of memory.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493855

EDCS 38200012

PHI 313644

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 15

Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 171-173 fig.37

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